

Context:

The 2-year project “Can we measure the effectiveness of public investments in urban climate resilience?” submitted by Dr. Marta Olazabal for the AXA Post-Doctoral Fellowships 2017 Second Campaign was awarded in 2017.

The project’s description is here: <https://www.axa-research.org/en/project/marta-olazabal>

Project’s website: <https://clic.bc3research.org/>

The project started in September 2018 and finalised in May 2021 (it was granted an extension due to COVID-19).

I, Marta Olazabal, am sharing the technical proposal of this project so that it is of help to future candidates. Make good use of it. And lots of luck.

CANDIDATE'S NAME: MARTA OLAZABAL

PROJECT TITLE: CAN WE MEASURE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PUBLIC INVESTMENTS IN URBAN CLIMATE RESILIENCE?

1. Research project and innovativeness (5 pages max.)

a. Long-term objectives and specific aims

After the Paris agreement that put stronger emphasis on the development of policies to adapt to climate change and on the definition of financing mechanisms, there is a patent need to track whether actual efforts towards adaptation are being sufficient (1–3). **Adaptation tracking will require a long-term effort** in which, as actions towards adaptation are being implemented, we **develop and improve methods and metrics to assess their effectiveness** while the uncertainty regarding climate models reduces. **This project contributes to this long-term challenge** by advancing the science of climate change adaptation and providing evidence about the progress being made in particular, by cities. **Why cities?** Cities are important and decisive actors in the international climate policy context (4). Hundreds of cities have started preparing for climate change impacts and are members of active networks such as C40 and the Compact of Mayors. Cities are also the places where higher investments will need to be made, because of their higher vulnerabilities and current environmental conditions (5, 6). Because of this, measuring the progress made by cities is a critical and required step to assess the global advances.

In line with this long-term challenge, the **general objective of this project** is to respond to the question of whether and how we can **measure the effectiveness of current or planned public investments** (meaning those resulting from interventions, plans and policies developed by the public administration) **in urban climate resilience. Are urban adaptation policies aligned with future risks?** This will be achieved first, by identifying and characterising specific adaptation actions and second, by comparing them against their future risks. This approach will be tested in a large-n set of cities that cover different geographic realities and diverse socio-economic contexts to obtain both city-specific results and world-wide general trends.

The **specific cutting-edge aims** of the project involve:

- (1) **The creation of a database (DB) to track urban climate change adaptation initiatives** (following 7) taking a set of 120 cities for which risk damage functions focused on tail events (high-impact, low-probability events) have been already developed (8, 9).
- (2) **The development and testing of risk-based metrics to measure the effectiveness** of identified planned or implemented measures to reduce vulnerability or increase resilience to climate change.
- (3) **The validation of the results in an in-depth case study** where stakeholders will be engaged in a process where specific city-region results (including tracking documents and risks metrics) will be revised and usability of the outputs will be contrasted.

b. Progress beyond the state-of-the-art

Planning for adaptation to climate change has emerged as a central component of climate policy over the last decade (10). Climate adaptation planning addresses current and future vulnerabilities by acting on the level of risk and strengthening adaptive capacities and resilience. The **Paris Agreement in 2015** set an ambitious pathway for adaptation that goes beyond national boundaries and urges nations, regions and cities to act on climate change together with other public and private stakeholders (11).

As interest in adaptation increases—including investment in adaptation policies, programs and actions—there is a **need to track whether these investments are effective** in reducing vulnerability and building resilience. This requires new methods, tools, and frameworks to track the actual progress on adaptation (1).

Adaptation tracking has been defined as the systematic collection, processing and analysis

of data and information to describe, assess and explain adaptation (policy) stability and change over time and across contexts. The ability to track adaptation progress is **highly relevant for governments** at different scales looking to prioritise their investments to effectively adapt and to define their strategies to access climate adaptation funding, especially in developing countries (12, 13). Likewise, it is fundamental to reduce policy uncertainties and provide the right **guidance to the private sector** such as robust criteria to define their funding strategies (14). However, challenges emerge due to the ambiguity of the concept of adaptation (what can be considered adaptation?) and the lack of comparable, aggregable metrics to measure the progress made on adaptation as compared to mitigation (e.g. greenhouse gas emissions) (13).

Efforts made to-date to track adaptation, however, are far from being comparable to those to track mitigation progress, and faces a number of **challenges**, including the lack of consistent definitions and practices, agreed metrics, comparable baselines, standardised approaches to data collection and robust guidance (see e.g. 12, 15, 16). In current adaptation tracking practice, the existence and nature of climate change adaptation policies has been used as an indicator of progress. Relevant studies have documented, examined, and compared adaptation policies at the national level (see e.g. 17), lower government-level policies (12, 16, 18), and communities (19). Due to the early stage of adaptation planning and because these plans by nature involve long-term objectives and high uncertainty, some of the main questions raised in current adaptation tracking research are **whether and how they will be implemented and what is required for these plans to successfully achieve their objectives.**

At the local level, it is important to recognise that **adaptation planning is relatively new and implementation is in its early stages.** The earliest local adaptation plans began emerging about ten years ago and are an increasingly important component of the international urban policy agenda (20). **However, the development of policies and plans on its own while instructive on adaptation progress, may not actually lead to vulnerability or risk reduction.**

On the one hand, there is evidence that local authorities, for instance, have often used climate mitigation policies to **recodify existing strategies without having substantial impact** on emissions reduction (21). This may suggest that a similar behaviour could be expected from climate adaptation strategies.

On the other hand, establishing valid methods for measuring the outcomes of adaptation policies in a similar way it is done for mitigation policies (see e.g. 22) is elusive as **many of the impacts of climate change will be felt in the long term** and therefore are not easy to measure or estimate (23).

In light of this, a **potential window-dressing use of adaptation policies evidenced by a general lack of implementation, calls for the need to look at the effectiveness** of increasingly emerging adaptation policies and plans by characterising current or planned adaptation investments and by defining appropriate metrics that are able to assess the effectiveness and appropriateness of these investments to reduce urban climatic risks.

Based on the latest scientific advances and emerging societal needs, this project aims to advance science by exploring this issue. Rather than starting developing a theoretical work, in this project, I propose to use, from the very beginning, a database of cities (geographically, socially and economically representative) and focus on specific risks (coastal, see **section 2**) to directly implement, test and validate ideas, methods and metrics. This will help to offer, in an integrated way, an **evidence-based scientific advance towards the measurement of adaptation progress in cities that can be replicable (to larger number of cities, to other risk typologies) and transferable (to the policy and scientific community).**

c. Innovative nature of the research proposed

It is argued that, one of the greatest challenges in decision-making under climate change uncertainty is to determine the level of adaptation investment proportionate to the climate-related risks a particular system is facing (24). Yet, this topic has received little attention so far. **Research has focused either on the policy process of adaptation to climate change (15) or in the modelling of current or future vulnerability or climatic risks (25).** Clearly, little focus has

been given on how to connect these two. According to Hall et al. (24) the relevant question would be *How much adaptation is enough?* In this project, I add to this by questioning ***Is planned adaptation enough?***

So far, as reviewed in the previous section, adaptation tracking has focused on policy processes. Policy documents and commitments are being tracked, governmental structures and organisation are being analysed in order to respond to the question of what is being done and how is being done (**tracking of adaptation governance – how? - and adaptation outputs – what?**). Given the limited focus of this line of research, Robert Briesbroek, whose work on climate change adaptation governance is highly acknowledged in the international scientific community, recently recognised during the European Climate Change Adaptation Conference – ECCA in Glasgow this June 2017, that **the adaptation tracking community is paying little attention to the assessment of whether actual governmental efforts are truly reducing vulnerability.**

Indeed, an important link is missing: Is planned adaptation meeting its goals? Is planned adaptation in fact reducing current or future vulnerability and increasing resilience? **Will planned adaptation be successful?** This is what has been defined as the assessment of adaptation outcomes, which links adaptation outputs (actions) to vulnerability and risks reduction.

Notably, the definition of “successful adaptation” is an issue at stake. There is no consensus on how to define it and there are multiple, sometimes competing, interpretations of success. Both in research and in practice, successful adaptation is interpreted differently (23), reflecting the messiness of the adaptation concept itself (1). If adaptation action can be interpreted in different ways, the definition of success is equally divergent and ambiguous. Although an outcome-based evaluation of adaptation success would depend on values of evaluators (20), **a successful adaptation action should be evaluated against the objective and in the context it was designed for** (17) and under multiple criteria of effectiveness, efficiency, equity and distributional impacts (26).

In this line, the innovative nature of this proposal is clear. I intend to connect an output-based evaluation of adaptation (what is being done?) to an outcome-based evaluation (will that reduce climatic risks?). Revealing its groundbreaking nature, this mission is both a science-policy challenge (24) and is being contested (20).

Methodologically speaking, I plan to analyse current commitments in the form of public policy documents (outputs) and develop methods to assess the alignment of current adaptation investments with future risks (outcomes). **Both parts involve a high degree of innovation.**

On one hand, I will **characterise and evaluate outputs in terms of their policy, economic and scientific credibility and their legitimacy.** Although applied in the field of mitigation to assess the integrity of national commitments after the Paris agreement (27), the concept of ‘credibility’ has not been used in the climate adaptation literature. This opens the opportunity to innovate in this field and assess public adaptation policies and plans in these terms.

On the other hand, to evaluate outcomes, I will use a database of calculated world-wide city damage-functions (8) that estimate future risks until 2100 and enable the **identification of tail events, defined as those that have low probability but would involve profound damages.** Often, this type of risks is disregarded and only average damages are taken into account. My intention is to develop a methodology and define a set of metrics to assess the level of risk that current planned adaptation is considering, i.e. **whether planned adaptation will be effective in reducing this type of risks.**

d. Proposal bibliographical references (1 page max.)

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2. Research plan (7 pages max)

a. Methodology, incl. a description of the materials and methods or experimental strategies

(i) General approach and scope of the research

In a nutshell, the specific objectives of this project include the creation of a DB to track urban climate change adaptation initiatives, the development of assessment methods for the effectiveness of those initiatives to reduce vulnerability or increase resilience to climate change and, finally, the validation of the relevance and usability of the outputs.

Given the innovative character of this project and the huge effort-intensive activities planned, the project will narrow the focus and specifically pay attention to coastal cities facing specific impacts due to climate change: as sea-level rise and extreme events. This enables to use the DB on risk-damage functions already developed by BC3 colleagues which covers **120 world-wide coastal cities**. Abadie et al. (1, 2) assess coastal flood risk from sea-level rise and extreme events in 120 major cities around the world using an alternative stochastic approach that accounts for uncertainty. The approach allows assessing yearly evolution of damages from 2020 to 2100. Additionally, they develop two risk measures that put low-probability, high-damage events in the spotlight. This allows estimating the damages when a certain risk level is exceeded (e.g. 5% of the city's GDP) and also to identify "by when" adaptation interventions should be implemented. This work results in a database of 120 cities and their yearly evolution of expected damages.

Fig. 1. Step-by-step empirical approach

Based on this baseline information, this project's first step will involve the identification of climate change adaptation initiatives across the 120 cities and the analysis of these initiatives. Section (ii) below describes the systematic review protocol that will be used. Figure 1 illustrates the step-by-step empirical approach taken by the project.

After this, the output-based and the outcome-based evaluation will be performed. In this sense, to ascertain that such adaptation policies and plans will be effective in the long-term, first, their credibility will be assessed. This will be done following the methodology that I propose in Olazabal et al. (3) that is expanded in (iii) below. This characterisation and assessment will enable the identification of specific actions focused on reducing coastal impacts (sea-level rise and extreme events). After this screening, I will define adequate metrics to compare initiatives with city-damage functions (see iv below). Challenges include: the different level of specification of adaptation initiatives (policy-, plan-, project-level) and the lack of descriptive data on each initiative which can provide heterogeneous or not fully comparable information about their level of effectiveness.

Finally, I will develop an in-depth case study on a region to be selected depending on the large-n set of cities (see v below). This case study will involve interviews with the stakeholders to validate the results and analyse how measures of effectiveness could be improved.

(ii) Systematic review and protocols for the creation of the DB

Tracking of adaptation to climate change requires the development of protocols that facilitate the systematic review and identification, characterization and measurement of adaptation initiatives. This is even more required when there is a patent need for increased standardization and transparency in the methods used to synthesize climate change research (4).

I propose to use the following systematic method to identify adaptation initiatives (used in 5, and previously in 6): the documents will be retrieved on a city-by-city basis using the search engine Google with a two-stepped process. First, the city's municipal website will be identified and scanned for adaptation planning documents. Such documents should be motivated by climate change and should be adaptation-focused or a combination of mitigation and adaptation strategies. For the second step, if no adaptation documents are found on the website, the search engine of Google will be used looking for "adaptation AND climate change AND *city's name*" and the first

20 results will be retrieved based on title and page description

From previous experiences (e.g. 5, 6) we can expect that not all the cities in the sample will have planned or implemented adaptation actions. For example, from a set of 401 cities over 1 million inhabitants, Araos et al. (5) retrieved adaptation plans from only 74 cities. In our case, from the 120 cities in the original sample, it should be advisable to guarantee at least the inclusion in the final set of a large-n set of cities (> 20 cities) that cover different geographical locations and different socio-economic realities (developed and developing contexts). Logically, translation of some of the identified documents will be necessary (those not in English, Spanish or French, which are the ones that I could analyse in their original language).

(iii) Output-based evaluation approach: assessment of credibility of current and planned investments

Here, credibility of climate adaptation plans or policies is defined as the likelihood that such policies and plans will be successfully implemented and sustained in the long-term or, at least, for the term they have been originally defined for by assigned responsible parties and in view of interested parties. In Olazabal et al. (3), I define a conceptual framework for this assessment in which aspects such as **(a) policy and economic credibility, (b) scientific and technical credibility and (c) legitimacy** are used as ‘umbrella’ to assess credibility. This results in 17 indicators and 53 metrics that analyse aspects such as (a) funding, consistency and coherency, prioritisation and timing, past performance, assigned responsibilities, public opinion, legislation and regulatory nature, networks membership, leadership and support (b) impacts and vulnerability assessment, adaptation options assessment, Monitoring, Evaluation and Reporting (MER) processes, learning mechanisms, uncertainty awareness and (c) transparency and dialogue, engagement of stakeholders and civil society’ and equity and justice. Metrics defining these concepts will be used to characterise and compare climate change adaptation plans and policies across the selected cities.

(iv) Outcome-based evaluation approach: Definition of risk-based metrics

The information provided by the **120 cities’ damage-functions** is characterised by the following: (a) the use of local relative sea-level rise projections for three IPCC scenarios for each city which incorporate not only eustatic sea-level but also other processes identified at each site, (b) the use of a stochastic diffusion model that enables to account for uncertainty, which provides information about the damage distribution at any given point in time and (c) the calculations of city-specific assessment of risk, drawn up by calculating two risk measures: (i) the VAR(95%), which represents the economic losses corresponding to the 95th percentile of the distribution of damage; and (ii) the ES(95%), which gives the average damage of the worst 5% of cases. Experience shows that “disasters are improbable but they do happen”, so policy makers need to consider them (7: 131). This way to look at risks, widely applied in financial economics, would **enable cities to define acceptable level of risks** and therefore, adaptation actions that should be implemented to avoid exceeding those acceptable risk levels. I propose to the opposite evaluation, i.e. analyse whether current initiatives are considering these risks. For this, I will develop a methodology to assess the effectiveness of such initiatives based on a set of risk-based metrics. As previously noted, challenges include: the different level of specification of adaptation initiatives (policy-, plan-, project-level) and the lack of descriptive data on each initiative which can result in heterogeneous or not fully comparable information about their level of effectiveness. I propose to address this challenge by including different levels of assessment which can provide more accurate information in each step. City-specific results and global trends will be obtained. Relevance and usability of the results will be contrasted with stakeholders in an in-depth case study.

(v) Strategy for the selection and development of the in-depth case study – PLANNED MOBILITY

The **selection of the in-depth case study has been planned to be realised during the development of the project and in M08 the latest** (see Gantt chart below). The selection will be based on the final large-n set of selected cities, setting as a criterion the selection of a developing region with enough adaptation activity and containing at least 2 cities of interest. **To facilitate logistics and increase the scientific impact of the project, it is envisaged the use of the current international networks at the Basque Centre for Climate Change, BC3**, centre that will

host the candidate Dr. Olazabal.

As a result of the COP22 celebrated in Marrakech in 2016, a new network aimed to build capacity around climate change issues emerged: the “**International Climate Change Centres of Excellence and Think Tanks for Capacity Building, INCCETT 4CB**”. The Network aims to boost coherence and improve coordination between major global centres of excellence and think tanks, with a view of enhancing the impact of capacity building activities. BC3 is one of its members. Other **founding members with offices located in focus and non-focus countries** such as Argentina, Thailand or Morocco, include:

- 4C Maroc - Centre de Compétences Changement Climatique
- IAI - Inter American Institute for Global Change Research
- IDDRI - Institut du Développement Durable et des Relations Internationales
- RedeClima Brazil
- (CR)2 - Center for Climate and Resilience Research, Chile
- IRI - International Research Institute for Climate and Society of Columbia University
- DIE - German Development Institute □ NCSC - National Climate Change Strategy Research and International Cooperation Center, China
- Consortium of Finnish Universities T3- Tampere
- SEI - Stockholm Environment Institute
- IISD – International Institute for Sustainable Development
- African Centre for Technology Studies

With the view of improving coordination and **boost excellent research**, this project, will make use of this network to select and develop the in-depth case study that will help to validate the results (relevance and usability) obtained in previous activities. **The candidate Dr. Marta Olazabal will choose a centre among those in the list above** depending on the large-n set of cities selected and on the identification of the most interesting region to develop a more detailed case study. The outgoing centre of her selection will collaborate in the in-depth case study by providing assistance and contacts during a **scientific staying planned for a maximum of 6 months**.

(vi) Delivering cutting-edge research on adaptation tracking

The work will be developed in collaboration with key researchers from the Grantham Research Institute (LSE, UK) (Alina Averchenkova, Elisa Sainz de Murieta), McGill University (Canada) (Alexandra Lesnikowski), and the University of Leeds (Priestley International Centre for Climate, UK) (James Ford). This will enable to continually **contrast the innovative and ground-breaking nature of the research as progress is being made**. Additionally, this will be retrofitted with a **continuous review of the state-of-the-art** on topics related to adaptation tracking and risk metrics during the whole project's life.

References to this section:

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b. Work packages and tasks (1 page max.)

Fig. 2. Visual structure of Working Packages (WPs)

WP1 Fine-Tuning of the scientific concept

In this WP, I will fine-tune the concept, framework and approaches that will lead the full technical development in the following WPs. To guarantee innovation and cutting-edge research, I will maintain a continuous review of the state-of-the-art on topics related to adaptation tracking and risk metrics during the whole project's life. The conceptual framework and approach will be iteratively contrasted upon this surveillance. **Tasks include: (1.1) Revision of the conceptual framework and approaches, and (1.2) Continuous review of the state-of-the-art (science and policy).**

WP2 Creation of the database of to track urban climate change adaptation

WP2 will be devoted to the creation of the urban climate change adaptation tracking database. Based on the pre-selection of the 120 coastal cities for which we have risk-damage functions, this DB will first identify and analyse adaptation plans or policies directed to reduce vulnerability and increase resilience and second, will catalog specific coastal measures. The credibility assessment of these climate resilience plans will be analysed following Olazabal et al. 2017. **Tasks include: (2.1) Systemic review of climate adaptation plans and policies in DB cities, (2.2) Assessment of the credibility of such plans and policies, and (2.3) Identification of specific planned or implemented coastal protection measures.**

WP3 Definition and testing of metrics to measure progress towards faced risk

Once the DB is developed (WP2), I will need to compare current planned or implemented measures with factual risks that cities will face in the following 100 years. This requires the development of specific metrics to compare effectiveness of measures to reduce vulnerabilities and increase resilience in time. **Tasks include: (3.1) Review of the literature on measurement of adaptation progress, (3.2) Definition of risk-based metrics and (3.3) Testing of the metrics in selected cities.**

WP4 In-depth case study

This WP will focus on the definition of an in-depth case study based on the results of WP2 and WP3. The case study will focus on a specific region (to be decided) and will be based on interviews with stakeholders in this region in order to validate and contrast results of the scientific study. **Tasks include: (4.1) Selection of case study region, (4.2) Data collection: case study review and stakeholder meetings and (4.3) Analysis and conclusions.**

WP5 Packing the contribution to science and society

Collecting the results of previous WPs, this WP will be dedicated to the **preparation of scientific outputs (Task 5.1) and to the elaboration of executive summaries and policy briefings (Task 5.2).** This will then be used as a base material for WP6 (dissemination).

WP6 Dissemination

This WP will cover the **design and maintenance of an AXA project-specific website (Task 6.1), the dissemination through scientific conferences, scientific blogs and expert talks (Task 6.2) and public outreach activities (Task 6.3)** such as media (radio, press and TV) contributions, public talks and wider public blogs contributions. A dissemination video will be produced.

WP7 Project Management

This WP will be devoted to the general tasks related to project management, both from the scientific and economic point of view. **Tasks include: (7.1) Scientific management** (including the supervision of project progress and the preparation of early contingency plans if the milestones' compliance is at risk) **and (7.2) Economic management.**

c. Gantt chart

Note: Yellow shaded cells identify two **critical milestones for the verification of the good progress of the project:** (M2.3) identification of specific coastal protection measures will allow testing in WP3 and (M4.1) selection of the case study, will enable the initiation of contacts and travel organisation in the case study to develop scientific activities in WP4.

Task	Description	M01	M02	M03	M04	M05	M06	M07	M08	M09	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24
WP1	<i>Fine-tuning of the scientific and innovative concept</i>																								
1.1	Revision of the conceptual framework and approaches																								
1.2	Continuous review of the state-of-the-art (science and policy)																								
WP2	<i>Creation of the database of to track urban CC adaptation</i>																								
2.1	Systemic review of climate adaptation plans and policies in DB cities																								
2.2	Assessment of the credibility of such plans and policies																								
2.3	Identification of specific planned or implemented coastal measures																								
WP3	<i>Definition and testing of metrics to measure progress towards faced risk</i>																								
3.1	Review of the literature on measurement of adaptation progress																								
3.2	Definition of risk-based metrics																								
3.3	Testing of the metrics in selected cities																								
WP4	<i>In-depth case study</i>																								
4.1	Selection of case study region																								
4.2	Data collection: case study review and stakeholder meetings																								
4.3	Analysis and conclusions																								
WP5	<i>Packing the contribution to science and society</i>																								
5.1	Preparation of scientific outputs																								
5.2	Preparation of executive summaries and policy briefings																								
WP6	<i>Dissemination</i>																								
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